

Study Procedure

Procedure based on “Guidelines for including grey literature and conducting multivocal literature reviews in software engineering” by Garousi et al. (2019)

Planning GLR

The need/motivations

- The increasing popularity of generative AI and its impact on software development. e.g., [“Generative AI for Software Practitioners” by Ebert and Louridas \(IEEE Software, 2023\)](#)
- We already have initial evidence these tools are and will influence software development. We still do not know to what extent, e.g., [“Taking Flight with Copilot: Early insights and opportunities of AI-powered pair-programming tools” by Bird et al. \(ACM Queue, 2022\)](#)
- There are recent code review’s SLR/SM that cover the traditional literature.
 - “A Systematic Literature Review and Taxonomy of Modern Code Review” by Davila and Nunes (2021) and “Modern Code Reviews - A Survey of Literature and Practice” by Badampudi et al. (2023)
- “GL provides “current” perspectives and complements gaps of the formal literature [25].” (Garousi et al., 2019, p. 108)

Goal: Our main goal is to investigate what has been discussed about generative AI technologies in the context.

Search process: Where to search: **Google** (general web search engine). It indexes online resources commonly used by software developers.

- [Stack Overflow Survey 2023](#): “Learning to code from online resources (e.g., videos, blogs, forum) increased from 70% to 80% since the 2022 survey.”

Documents selection:

Search string:

- Code review:
 - The most recent SM of code review research (Badampudi et al. (2023)) defined the following keywords for the search string (“[...] combining each keyword with a logical “OR” operation and adding a wildcard operator (*).”)
 - code review
 - patch accept
 - commit review
 - pull request

- modern code inspect
 - Perhaps “patch accept”, “pull request”, and “modern code inspect” return many documents unrelated to the code review practice, burdening the GL review.
- Generative AI:
 - Following the topic of the special issue: “generative AI” OR “generative artificial intelligence”.
- We checked the possible string combinations here. Based on some testing using the aforementioned strings, (“code review” AND “artificial intelligence”) looks like the better combination.
- **Meeting 19/10/2023:** we defined the search string as **“code review” AND (“generative AI” OR “generative artificial intelligence” OR “ChatGPT” OR “Copilot”)**
 - We included the two most popular AI-based tools according to [Stack Overflow Survey 2023](#): ChatGPT and Copilot.

Selection criteria:

Definition of the code review process:

- Step 1: Create and prepare a code change (author)
 - Step 2: Select reviewers (author)
 - Step 3: Code checking (reviewer)
 - Step 4: Providing feedback (reviewer)
 - Step 5: Address reviewer feedback (author)
 - Step 6: Decide the outcome of the review (reviewer)
- Inclusion Criteria (IC):
 - IC1: The document is about the adoption of generative AI explicitly for the code review process (a specific step or the whole process), including examples of how well-known tools can be used or adapted, their influence on the practice, and expectations.
 - IC2: The document is about a tool exploring generative AI to explicitly support the code review process (a specific step or the whole process), including the homepage or repository of novel approaches.
- Exclusion Criteria (EC):
 - EC1: Not written in English.
 - EC2: Not text-based content (i.e., videos or slide presentations).
 - EC3: Duplicate content.
 - EC4: The document is a forum or group discussion thread.
 - EC5: The document is the homepage of a popular AI-based tool, such as GitHub Copilot or ChatGPT.

- EC6: The document is about using generative AI for code review, but the proposed approach takes as input a whole Git repository, folder, or file.
- EC7: The document is unavailable.
- Snowballing approach: no

Selection and filtering process:

- Access the document and check each IC/EC, marking "true" if the text applies and "false" if it does not.
- The document is included in the study if: (i) at least one IC is "true"; and (ii) no EC is "true" (i.e. all EC="false")

Data extraction:

- Save documents in PDF format.
- Extract:
 - Title
 - Author
 - Date
 - Author's background

Execution of GLR

- **05/10/2023:** First **meeting** about GL MCR+GenAI
 - To do:
 - Nicole will create a folder on Google Drive to share study materials. She'll also create an Overleaf document with the paper template.
 - We will begin to define the study protocol.
- **09/10/2023:** Nicole shared the first draft of the study procedure (this doc)
- **15/10/2023:** Tests with options of search string
- **19/10/2023:** Meeting
 - We defined the search string as **"code review" AND ("generative AI" OR "generative artificial intelligence" OR "ChatGPT" OR "Copilot")**
 - We included the two most popular AI-based tools according to [Stack Overflow Survey 2023](#): ChatGPT and Copilot.
 - To do:
 - Jorge will perform the search and consolidation of results.
 - For the first 20 results, each one of us will individually evaluate whether or not the document should be included (considering the current selection criteria). Also, we will check which RQ each document is related to.

- After the individual evaluation, we will check for disagreements and refine the process.
 - As the next steps, Nicole will individually evaluate and qualitatively analyze the first 100 results. Then, we will check the saturation: each one will analyze another 20 results, and then we will check if anything new has emerged.
- **20/10/2023:** Jorge performed the search and shared the result spreadsheet.
- **23/10/2023:** We all finished the **individual evaluation** of the first **20 results**.
- **24/10/2023:** Nicole consolidated the results of the first assessment iteration. We all **discuss key points of disagreement** (via WhatsApp). Outcome:
 - Take a definition of the code review process and adopt it as a guideline to decide whether a document is related to the practice or not.
 - Refinement of the inclusion criteria: IC1: The document is about the adoption of generative AI explicitly for the code review process (a specific step or the whole process); IC2: The document is about a tool exploring generative AI to explicitly support the code review process (a specific step or the whole process).
 - Exclude documents related to threads in forums or discussion groups and pages of well-known AI tools, such as Copilot.
 - Pending decisions: snowball? next steps?
- **26/10/2023: Meeting** - Nicole and Jorge
 - We checked the selection criteria (now everything is fine) and decided not to use snowballing.
 - Based on the revised selection criteria, Nicole and Jorge will go back to the first 20 search results and check them again.
 - The next round of review will depend on the level of agreement in this new evaluation. If there is no need to review the criteria again, Nicole will continue with the analysis.
- **27/10/2023:** Nicole and Jorge finished the new evaluation round of the first 20 results. Given whether or not the document was included in the study, **the two agreed in all 20 cases**. We agree that Nicole can start the next iteration (I3): filtering the first 100 results, followed by the qualitative analysis of the included documents.
- **03/11/2023:** Nicole finished evaluating the first 100 results based on the selection criteria, including 44 documents in the study. Now, she start the qualitative analysis of the included results using coding.
- **08/11/2023:** Meeting to share initial insights and to clarify some aspects.
 - During the analysis, Nicole identified some questions. Today, we discussed how to deal with them.

- Some documents are about approaches using GAI for code review, but the input is a git repository, a folder, or a file. As code review practice is focused on code changes, we decided to exclude these documents from the study. Therefore, we will create an exclusion criteria for such cases.
 - Some search results are posts with links, e.g., a LinkedIn post with just a link to a blog. Since we chose not to snowball, we confirm that these cases are disregarded.
 - Nicole also shared some initial results and insights from the study and presented the progress of the work. We talked about the possibility of submitting a more complete paper to the IST journal in addition to the originally planned IEEE Software Special Issue.
- **21/11/2023:** Guidelines to verify Coding Saturation
 - We started discussing how to evaluate saturation via WhatsApp, but we decided to talk and specify this procedure in a synchronous meeting.
- **24/11/2023: Meeting:** Nicole, Jorge e Igor.
 - Nicole will extract the excerpts from each document that support the classification in a given code.
 - How will we check the coding:
 - Nicole will randomly select a subset of documents for Igor and Jorge to evaluate the coding. Each subset will already have the document classification made by Nicole and the excerpts that support the decision.
 - Jorge and Igor will individually check the codebook and then the subset, checking whether they agree or not with the classification.
 - After the individual process, we will evaluate the next steps.
- **27/11/2023 - 01/12/2023:** Jorge and Igor individually checked the codebook and a subset of 8 documents each.
- **02/12/2023 - 11/12/2023:** Nicole refined the codebook and extraction based on the feedback from Jorge and Igor. She also started the paper to report the study.
- **12/12/2023:** Meeting to clarify some aspects of the codebook and discuss next steps.
- **19/12/2023:** An initial version of our analysis was submitted and is under consideration in the Special Issue on Generative AI for Software Engineering of IEEE Software.
- **08/01/2024 - 19/02/2024:** Write a full paper to report our study findings.